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Review Article

**SODIUM LAURELSUPLHATE AS AN INGREDIENT IN
TOOTHPASTE**¹Dr Sikandar, ²Dr Syeda Momena Rashid, ³Dr Madiha Rafi¹Karachi Medical and Dental College²Karachi Medical and Dental College³Karachi Medical and Dental College**Abstract:**

Sodium laurelsuplhate (sls) is an ingredient of dentifrice (toothpaste) which act as a foaming agent and have bactericide properties but it is found to have deleterious side effects on oral mucosa including increase desquamation increase tendency of recurrent apthous ulcers(RAS) , luekoedema besides it also delays wound healing and decrease the cariostatic activity of fluoride.

Keywords: sodium laurelsuplhate, toothpaste, recurrent apthous ulcers, desquamation, , stearth-30.

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INTRODUCTION:

Sodium laurel sulphate (SLS) is a foaming agent added in dentifrices in concentration of 0.5-2.0% which is also a manufactured bactericide. SLS lowers the surface tension, penetrates and loosens surface deposits and emulsifies or suspends the debris which the dentifrice removes from the tooth.(9) It is proposed that the detrimental effect of SLS on the oral mucosa leads to exposure of basal epithelium intensifying the effect of RAS (4).

SLS has an irritating effect leading to exfoliation of mucosa (7). It is known to cause ulceration and desquamation as well as increasing the penetration of non-electrolytes, which damages the permeability barrier of oral mucosa (1a). SLS is also likely to trigger hypersensitivity, some experiments also indicate that SLS is capable of reacting with fluoride accumulated on dental enamel and this interaction has a critical consequence on inhibiting the cariostatic activity of fluoride (9).

When any surgical procedure is done or when a wound is formed in the oral cavity, particularly in the gingiva, healing requires formation of collagen and fibroblasts and an important part of wound healing is the ability of fibroblasts to repopulate a wound and produce collagen. SLS is reported to cause delayed wound healing at the respective surgical sites. It acts as an obstacle in the activity of human gingival fibroblasts (HGF) which is a prime factor for healing including prolonged recovery of the wound(3).

In a recent study, SLS was diagnosed as causing hyperkeratosis and acanthosis of underlying epithelium causing leukoedema in some patients. Successfully, the condition spontaneously resolved on using SLS free toothpastes (8).

It is suggested that SLS free toothpastes and dentifrices decrease the span and extent of aphthous stomatitis and reduce the tenderness of mucosa (10). These dentifrices are also beneficial and favorable to use after surgical incisions. The use of Zandium with steareth-30 as a mild alternative to SLS has shown improvement in oral health causing minimal sloughing of gingiva and maintaining epithelial integrity (10.1)(2.1). There are multiple substitutes proven to diminish the side effects of SLS in dentifrices.

Literature review:

Several studies reveal the adverse effects of SLS on oral mucosa. Antonija Tadin *et al.* conducted a study to determine the toxic effects of fluoride and sodium laurel sulphate on buccal epithelial cells. Forty

participants were assigned into two groups. Three types of toothpastes of different brands were used (non-fluoride and non-SLS, fluoride and non SLS, and the fluoride and SLS) for 6 months, each for 2 months. After 60 days the buccal epithelial cells were examined. The toothpaste with SLS and fluoride exhibited higher prevalence of pyknotic cells, cells with karyorrhexis, and nuclear buds compared to the toothpastes of the same brand with fluoride and without SLS, and without fluoride and without SLS, for the same interval. Based on the findings it was concluded that fluoride doesn't cause any cytotoxic or genetic effects but SLS significantly increases the incidence of nuclear morphological transition in buccal epithelial cells. (1) Another clinical trial was conducted by L Chahine to assess the effect of Sodium lauryl Sulfate on recurrent aphthous ulcers. This study calculated the prevalence of recurrent aphthous ulcers while using dentifrices with and without sodium lauryl sulfate. A single-blind crossover study was done. Statistical analysis revealed considerable reduction in recurrent aphthous ulcers after the use of SLS free dentifrice for two months compared to SLS containing dentifrice which was used for the same period. The results indicated that SLS free dentifrice should be used for individuals suffering from recurrent aphthous ulcers (2) SLS was also thought to cause oral desquamation. Bente Brokstad Herlofson performed an experiment using toothpastes containing SLS and pastes containing cocoamidopropylbetaine (CAPB) to assess the desquamative effects of both. Seven toothpastes containing different concentrations and/or type of detergent were used i.e. SLS (0.5, 1.0, 1.5), CAPB (0.64, 1.27, 1.90) and a placebo in 28 healthy females. The assigned toothpaste was applied to the teeth via a cap splint and the mucosa of the upper jaw. The splints containing 1cm of each paste were used twice a day for 2 minutes over a period of 4 days, following which the subjects were examined for oral desquamation. No other oral hygiene products were used during the test sessions. Detergent free toothpastes were used for brushing for ten days between each test period. Forty five desquamative reactions were recorded in 21 of 27 participants (one was disqualified) during the study. Forty two reactions were reported during the SLS periods and three were reported during CAPB periods. SLS containing toothpastes increased the prevalence of oral mucosa desquamation compared with the toothpaste containing CAPB. This study suggests that using SLS as a detergent in toothpastes can cause mucosal irritation and less toxic detergents like CAPB are advisable. (3)

We review the compositions of commonly used toothpastes and found that many commonly use toothpaste brands have SLS as their ingredient, given

below are this list of some SLS containing and non-SLS containing toothpaste brands:

SLS brands	manufacturer company name
• <i>Aquafresh</i> (11)	GlaxoSmithKline
• <i>Closeup</i> . (12)	Unilever
• <i>Sparkle</i> . (13)	Medline Industries
• <i>Paradontax</i> . (14)	GlaxoSmithKline
• <i>Pepsodent</i> . (15)	Unilever
• <i>Oral-B</i> .(16)	P&G
• <i>Crest</i> . (17)	P&G
• <i>Aim's</i> (18)	Church&Dwight
• <i>Tom's of Maine</i> . (19)	Tom's of Maine,inc.
• <i>Colgate</i> . (20)	Colgate-Palmolive Company
• <i>Doctor will toothpaste</i> . (21)	YIRH HEALTHY LIVING COMPANY
• Non-SLS Toothpaste.	Manufacturer company name
• <i>Macleans</i> (22)	GlaxoSmithKline
• <i>Sensodyne</i> (23)	GlaxoSmithKline
• <i>Jason</i> . (24)	Jason Natural Products Inc.
• <i>Miswak (hamdard)</i> (25)	Hamdard Laboratories
• <i>Armandhammer</i> (26)	Church&Dwight

Sodium lauryl sulfate has some side effects, and future work should therefore be concentrated on finding other possible toothpaste detergents without these side effects.(9.1)

As an alternative one substance steareth-30 shows good results, Steareth 30 (polyethylene glycol ether of stearyl alcohol, 30 ethylene oxide) a mild surfactant with lower foaming *properties* 'Toothpaste containing Steareth 30 surfactant generated fewer lesions and a lower average soft tissue lesion severity score compared to the toothpaste containing SLS surfactant (2.2) **it is also found** that application of a toothpaste containing the surfactant Steareth 30 has very low rate of soft tissue desquamation compared to a toothpaste containing SLS surfactant(2.3)and Steareth 30 toothpaste led to significantly fewer soft tissue lesions compared to the SLS toothpaste(2.4). In addition a *Zendium™*, a toothpaste containing enzymes and proteins (amyloglucosidase, glucose oxidase, lactoperoxidase, lysozyme, lactoferrin and immunoglobulin), is formulated with Steareth 30 was reported to have the lowest potential for irritancy of several commercial toothpastes including those with SLS(2.5), zendium is also beneficial for mucosa because it is found that mucosa exposed to SLS alone showed an increase in permeability to water, the

addition of Triclosan and Zinc to SLS appeared to prevent this effect. (5)

In conclusion, despite all the merits of non-sls dentifrice's and demerits of sls containing dentifrices according to above mention literature, FDA still mark SLS safe to be use in personal care products even in recent studies(6).

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